

Entrepreneurship Development In Agribusiness Enterprises In Pakistan

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Abstract

The present study attempts to investigate entrepreneurship development in agribusiness enterprises in Pakistan. The study employs a deductive approach which is based on cross-sectional data. The study utilizes 220 usable samples to conclude. By using AMOS software, the findings of the survey highlight a significant and positive effect of the economic factor (EF), social factor (SF), managerial factor (MNF), marketing factor (MF), psychological factor (PF), and cultural factor (CF) on entrepreneurial development (ED). The study outcomes would provide guidelines for providing adequate access to credit facilitates from commercial banks and other microfinance institutions. Besides, the findings would also help create a favorable environment for ED. Finally, the conclusions would enrich the depth of entrepreneurship literature.

JEL Classification: L26, Q13, L32

Introduction

At present, the development of entrepreneurship has almost become a significant issue for every world economy (Soomro, Shah, & Lashari, 2020). It is a process of engaging market-based methods to hunt business, social or financial goals (Grimes *et al.*, 2013). The different circumstances or entrepreneurial characteristics assist entrepreneurs in taking innovative activities to boost their initial stance, allowing them to achieve new opportunities (Baron, 2008; Mei *et al.*, 2017). These support their decision-making processes (Shepherd *et al.*, 2009). According to Parrish and Foxon (2006), entrepreneurs are the economy's significant agents, which get their environmental, social, and goals. In other words, entrepreneurship has the dynamic process of generating wealth (Shailesh *et al.*, 2013; Soomro *et al.*, 2018). Such wealth is earned by individuals who take the major risks, i.e. time, equity, and carrier commitment, to offer value to some product or services. Simply, it is the use of energy for starting and building a venture (Mishra *et al.*, 2010). The advance of agricultural entrepreneurship has an effective strategy to enhance agricultural production worth and open up businesses.

Despite this, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs confront massive challenges in education, technological development, cultural and economic development (Mei *et al.*, 2017; Soomro *et al.*, 2020). In Pakistan, entrepreneurs are willing and eager to perform their entrepreneurial activities (Ali *et al.*, 2011). They also intend to become self-bosses through achieving sustainable entrepreneurship by converting their ideas into actual business practices (Shah & Soomro, 2017; Usman & Ahmed, 2018; Soomro & Shah, 2021). The government of Pakistan has acknowledged the contribution of agribusiness small and micro agro-enterprises (SMEs) in generating jobs, developing people's living standards, and subsequently, an overall effect on the economy. Therefore, investigating the factors that affect the entrepreneurship development in Agribusiness Enterprises among farmers in Pakistan is the need of the day. The present study examines the aspects of entrepreneurship development in agribusiness enterprises in Pakistan.

Literature Review And Conceptualization

Entrepreneurial development is necessary to boost economic growth. Olowa and Olowa (2015) claims that gender, age, marital status, and size of business have great importance in agribusiness. On the other hand, the primary occupation is negatively associated with agribusiness enterprise participation. Similarly, in Pakistan's context, Soomro *et al.* (2019) suggest that entrepreneurs' demographic characteristics, i.e. education, gender, experience, and age, are responsible for bringing entrepreneurs' success among the SMEs. Empirical evidence of Mishra *et al.* (2010) claimed that agricultural entrepreneurship enhances agricultural production worth and

opens up the sector for businesses. Polishing farmers' entrepreneurial skills can bring political, cultural, and socio-economic frameworks that ultimately reduce the hindrances and stimulate their farmers' entrepreneurial skills. Entrepreneurial development can be possible through capabilities (Ojonugwa&Alewo, 2016). In Tanzania, a low integration of farmers confronting more hindrances in accessing markets. Formal training, age, and the value of agricultural production are the significant elements that driving farmers to select a specific market to sell their produces (Kangile *et al.*, 2020). Among five Central and E, and agricultural production value and, Moldova, and Serbia, a study conducted by Borychowski *et al.* (2020) by producing the data on farms' resilience. The outcomes of the study claim that the production scale is the significant determinant of the resilience of farms. By applying the SEM path model, Mirjatet *et al.* (2019) claim a positive and significant influence of farmers' education, income, and experience on farmer's family are positively and meaningfully associated with family, casual and perpetual hired labor, seed, irrigation, and fertilizer (Adilet *et al.*, 2004).

As a result, the prominent feature of Pakistan's agrarian scenario is the prevalence of small assets. The affluence of small farmers is essential for Pakistani society's well-being (Adilet *et al.*, 2004). Agro-enterprise or agribusiness is a crucial segment that several rural SMEs activate and contain all participants in a vertical commodity structure from farmers, assemblers, processors, suppliers, and distributors to eventual domestic as international consumers. The agribusiness SMEs is of prominence to Pakistan as it enhances the economic development, creates jobs, accelerates growth and business solutions and eradicates poverty (Adilet *et al.*, 2004; Khan *et al.*, 2020). Besides, agriculture and agricultural-related business are a critical sector that contributes 24% of GDP (Mirjatet *et al.*, 2019).

In this way, the literature examines the different factors such as agribusiness, government, and private developmental programs, access to credit and loans, goods and services, competitive market and tax rates, human capitals, skilled and trained staffs, income level and demographic factors, which significantly promote the entrepreneurship development in the agriculture sector (Jancikova, 2004; Mirjatet *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2020). However, the literature hugely lacks investigating the different factors in examining the **entrepreneurship development in agribusiness enterprises in Pakistan. Based on such deficiencies, we developed the following model (Figure 1) for confirmation in Pakistan.**

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the study

ED is one of the most significant features of society's social stability and economic growth. According to Olowa and Olowa (2015), EF followed by SF and CF are regarded as substantial for agribusiness ED. Besides, the demographic constructs, i.e. gender, age, marital status, and business size, are significant predictors of agribusiness enterprise. The improvement of the economic environment is supportive for companies or SMEs (Olmos *et al.*, 2014). The empirical study of Rattanawiboonsom and Ali (2016) suggests that financial organizations are needed to develop proper steps to poverty alleviation and attain sustainable development goals (SDGs) in rural areas. In global markets, the political, social, cultural, and technological environments work as contributing factors in entrepreneurial success (Agwu&Onwuegbuzie, 2018). In the perception of Rokhman and Ahamed (2015), SF (education system, social status, and family background) and PF (locus of control, need for achievement, and propensity to risk) are reasonably protruding and substantial indicators to become entrepreneurs. Kothari (2013) investigates the social perspective of entrepreneurship, which reflects individuals'

specific castes, ethnic groups, social institutions, social values and norms, and culture significantly influence the level of entrepreneurship. Besides, the study also finds a positive effect of personality traits on entrepreneurship. Similarly, Yurchynska and Serdiuk (2017) support the PF for the business success of entrepreneurs. Price stabilization of agriculture products in agribusiness enterprises is substantial element of ED. Becchetti and Trovato (2002) view the lack of financial resources or financial barriers such as lack of external debt, equity capital, and credit restriction as the protagonist obstacles to SME's growth. An empirical study conducted by Sowoleet *al.* (2018) examined the effect of PF on youth's desire towards self-sustenance and entrepreneurial behavior. The study outcomes reveal that community and stressors close to home positively and significantly associated with a pattern of behavior and interest in entrepreneurship. Likewise, culture is a significant factor that differentiates the members of one category of people from others (Bagwell, 2006). Values as an essential constituent of culture play a significant role in developing the entrepreneurial culture. The evidence about entrepreneur motivation and the effect of family member involvement on business growth has a significant impact on SMEs' family business success (Rachmaniaet *al.*, 2012).

As a result, the literature witnessed the positive and significant effect of EC, SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF on ED in the different contexts (Becchetti&Trovato, 2002; Olmos *et al.*, 2014; Olowa&Olowa, 2015; Agwu&Onwuegbuzie, 2018). However, an exploration of these factors towards ED in Pakistan, particularly in agribusiness enterprises, is still at the infancy stage. Thus, we proposed the following hypotheses for investigating among agribusiness enterprises of Pakistan:

H1. EF positively and significantly affects ED.

H2. SF positively and significantly affects ED.

H3. MNF positively and significantly affects ED.

H4. MF positively and significantly affects ED.

H5. PF positively and significantly affects ED.

H6. CF positively and significantly affects ED.

METHODS

The study employed a deductive approach that utilizes cross-sectional data. We analyzed the data through AMOS version 26.0 for windows. This approach is applied by several scholars like Becchetti and Trovato (2002), Olmos *et al.* (2014), Olowa and Olowa (2015), Agwu and Onwuegbuzie (2018), and Memonet *al.* (2019). The study was conducted in different areas of Pakistan. We got the details of small and micro agribusinesses from the Bureau of Statistics from Pakistan. The units of analysis (respondents) were the small and micro agribusiness firm owners/managers. Henceforth, about forty agribusinesses were selected in each of the markets. We applied convenience sampling through a survey questionnaire. The study considered the proper ethical protocols of the participants. They were made aware of the utilization of the data, privacy, and confidentiality of their gained responses. The questionnaire contained demographic information of the farmers, perception of the entrepreneur on factors which affect agribusiness. We employed a Likert scale. Finally, 220 usable samples were applied for the final assessment.

Measures

We adapted all the items from the literature and slightly modified them in the Pakistani context. We measure the ED factor on seven items derived from the study of Ojonugwa and Omale (2016). The scale's sample item is "The government of Pakistan has been effective in creating an enabling environment for entrepreneurial development." Likewise, we adapted EF, SF, MNP, MF, PF, and CF factors from Olowa and Olowa (2015). The sample item for EF was "Stabilization of agricultural products prices"; SF (Tendency to group work); MNF "Ability to provide leadership by agribusiness manager"; MP "Effective advertising to attract new customers"; PF "Enthusiasm to achieve great things" and CF "Combining formal knowledge with indigenous knowledge".

RESULTS

Respondents' demography

Demography of respondents shows that 81.82% (n=180) respondents were male compared to female (18.18% or n=40). 50% (n=110) respondents were 41-50 years of age. 28.18% (n=62) were < 40 years of age. A minority of respondents, 21.82 % (n=48), are found to 51-60 years. A majority (78.18% or n=172) of respondents were married as compared to unmarried respondents (21.82 or n=48) (Table 1). A significant number, i.e. 65 respondents, have deprived formal education regarding education level, while 4.54 have with the other degrees or higher than secondary education. Likewise, a majority of respondents (56.36 or n=124) were experienced with 11-19 years. Finally, we found only 20% (n=44) with less than ten years (Table 1).

Table 1: Respondents' demography

Gender	Category	Frequency	Percent
	Male	180	81.82
	Female	40	18.18

	<i>Total</i>	220	100.0
Age	< 40 years	62	28.18
	41-50 years	110	50.00
	51-60 years	48	21.82
	<i>Total</i>	220	100.0
Marital status	Married	172	78.18
	Unmarried	48	21.82
	<i>Total</i>	220	100.0
Education level	Non formal education	65	29.54
	Primary	82	37.28
	Secondary	63	28.64
	Other	10	4.54
	<i>Total</i>	220	100.0
Business experience	< 10 year	44	20.00
	11-19 years	124	56.36
	20 and above years	52	23.64
	<i>Total</i>	220	100.0

Measurement model

We conducted factor loadings to assess the reliability of the individual indicator. The values of the loadings have observed with meaningful scores (> 0.70) (Hair *et al.*, 2017) (Table 2). However, two items (mnf3 and sd5) loaded above the required values of 0.70. Henceforth, unloaded items were excluded from further analysis (Hair *et al.*, 2010). The composite reliability (CR) of all the factors noticed in-between 0.842 and 0.896 (Table 2) or above the suggested scores (0.70) (Geffen *et al.*, 2000; Kline, 2010). Moreover, to assess an identical measure of constructs, we found values of the average variance extracted values (AVE) in-between 0.790- 0.891 for the rest of the variables of the model (> 0.50) (Hair *et al.*, 2010). Likewise, Cronbach's alpha noticed as satisfactory and acceptable for all of the variables (> 0.70) (Nunnally& Bernstein, 1994).

Table 2: *Measurement model*

Construct	Item code	Factor loadings	CR	AVE	A
ED	ed1	0.869	0.868	0.823	0.884
	ed2	0.856			
	ed3	0.850			
	ed4	0.842			
	ed6	0.830			
	ed7	0.809			
	EF	ef1			
ef2		0.868			
ef3		0.850			
ef4		0.821			
ef5		0.789			
SF	sf1	0.886	0.849	0.793	0.855
	sf3	0.874			
	sf2	0.820			
	sf4	0.813			
MNF	mnf1	0.882	0.879	0.790	0.832
	mnf2	0.867			
	mnf4	0.851			
	mnf5	0.820			
MF	mf2	0.878	0.875	0.863	0.898
	mf3	0.825			
	mf1	0.810			
	mf4	0.792			
PF	pf1	0.896	0.842	0.881	0.846

	pf2	0.884			
	pf4	0.862			
	pf3	0.823			
	pf5	0.803			
CF	cf1	0.865	0.890	0.819	0.867
	cf2	0.853			
	cf4	0.842			
	cf3	0.819			

Notes: AVE = summation of the square of the factor loadings

CR = square of the summation of the factor loadings

α = Cronbach's alpha

Note(s), ED=entrepreneurial development; EF=economic factor; SF=social factor; MNF=managerial factor; MF=marketing factor; PF=psychological factor; CF=cultural factor

Structural model

We employed structural equation modeling (SEM) to confirm the model fitness and hypotheses assessment. We reported Chi-square statistic and fit indices which are the significant and robust indicators of model fitness (Cheung, 2009). We ran the model through AMOS (figure 2). The scores of χ^2 appeared as non-significant (CMIN/df= 1.782; > p 0.005) (Figure 2), which show the initial indication of model fitness with the available data (Hair *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, the values of other indices, i.e. GFI=0.930; AGFI=0.922; NFI=0.939; CFI=0.945 and RMSEA= 0.040 recommend a relatively well-fitting model (cutoff value is 0.08) (Hair *et al.*, 2018) (Figure 2 and Table 3).

Table 3: Model fit indices

Model fit indicators	CMIN/df	GFI	AGFI	NFI	CFI	RMSEA
	2.658	0.930	0.922	0.939	0.945	0.040
Suggested values	< 3	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	< 0.05

Note: CMIN= χ^2 /Chi-square/df; DF= degree of freedom; GFI=goodness of fit index; AGFI=adjusted goodness of fit index; NFI= normed fit index; CFI= comparative fit index; RMSEA=root mean square error of approximation.

We applied maximum likelihood estimates based on the standard error (ER) and the critical ratio (CR) and significant path at the level of <0.01*** to confirm the proposed paths. The analysis confirms the positive and significant effect of EF on ED (SE=0.039; CR=5.487; p< 0.01) (Figure 2 and Table 4). Thus, H1 is supported. Besides, SEM confirm the positive and significant effect of SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF on ED [H2 (SE=0.078; CR=4.789) H3 (SE=0.040; CR=6.882) H4 (SE=0.062; CR=6.779) H5 (SE=0.050; CR=7.002) H6 (SE=0.027; CR=5.669; p< 0.01)] (Figure 2 and Table 4). Therefore, H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6 were supported.

Figure 2. Structural equation model

Table 4: SEM estimations

H.No.	Independent variables	Path	Dependent variables	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
H1	EF	→	ED	0.369	0.039	5.487	***	Accepted
H2	SF	→	ED	0.288	0.078	4.789	***	Accepted
H3	MNF	→	ED	0.233	0.040	6.882	***	Accepted
H4	MF	→	ED	0.399	0.062	6.779	***	Accepted
H5	PF	→	ED	0.288	0.050	7.002	***	Accepted
H6	CF	→	ED	0.353	0.027	5.669	***	Accepted

Note: SE=standard error; CR=critical ratio; p=significance level *** $p < 0.05$

ED=entrepreneurial development; EF=economic factor; SF=social factor; MNF=managerial factor; MF=marketing factor; PF=psychological factor; CF=cultural factor

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to investigate entrepreneurship development in agribusiness enterprises in Pakistan. The study employed a deductive approach in assessing the purpose. Concerning the hypotheses outcomes, the SEM outcomes found a positive and significant EF, SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF on ED. These outcomes are in line with previous studies, i.e. Rachmania *et al.* (2012); Olowa and Olowa (2015); Yurchynska and Serdiuk (2017); Agwu&Onwuegbuzie (2018). These findings reflect that EF, SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF factors are necessary for ED development. At the same time, ED is a prerequisite of the economic and social stability of society. The small and micro agribusiness firm owners/managers want to stabilize the prices of the agricultural products, income satisfaction, and access to knowledge about the statistics of the markets' facts and figures. They intend to suitable investments in agribusiness and usable infrastructure and support to agricultural export products.

From a social perspective, they need a tendency to group work, provision of insurance for entrepreneurs, and adequate bankruptcy Laws. Besides, from a managerial perspective, they want equitable sharing of benefits among employees, appreciation, and employee reassurance. Further, they are eager to provide leadership by

agribusiness managers. They want to further invention and innovation by reducing their previous failures and faults. They are also ambitious to utilize staffs' opinions and recommendations in rational decision-making. In the marketing domain, they want to make an effective advertisement for attracting new consumers without mediators, willing to drive direct sales of their products. They are enthusiastic about being familiar with national, local, and regional markets.

Psychologically and culturally, the respondents are interested in attaining great things, high self-reliance, and self-confidence. They want to show a higher tendency to self-employment and finding new incentives with personal creativity. They are determined for merging formal knowledge with native knowledge. They are going to support their families to view agribusiness entrepreneurship positively. They want to help from relatives and their friends to work with the Great Spirit.

In conclusion, the study's overall findings show a significant positive effect of factors such as EF, SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF on ED. In a simple sense, the ED is predicted by the various factors related to sociology, economics, psychology, marketing, culture, and management.

LIMITATIONS, IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The study is limited to quantitative modes where we collected the cross-sectional data. The study did not employ any concerned theory to underpin the conceptual framework. The study used convenience sampling through a survey questionnaire. Finally, the findings of the study are restricted to only 220 samples.

The study provides the substantial role of EF, SF, MNF, MF, PF, and CF for ED in Pakistan. The study outcomes would provide guidelines for providing adequate access to credit facilities from commercial banks and other microfinance institutions. It would guide the policymakers and concerned authorities to create a stimulating and conducive environment for entrepreneurial development. The promotion of ED activities or entrepreneurship would generate employment. The study would help access other modern technology for operation in Pakistan. The development of the infrastructure would bring sufficient growth would ultimately change the fortunes of entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

In the future, more longitudinal studies may be conducted to validate the outcomes of the study further. Mixed methods, i.e. qualitative and quantitative methods, are required to achieve the tasks in the future. The large samples may be employed to generalize the results. Finally, the concerned theories are suggested to apply in future studies.

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